

V2X communication coverage analysis for connected vehicles in intelligent transportation networks

A case study for the city of Xanthi, Greece

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Research Questions

- **Identification of possible optimizations of V2V and V2I communication performance in the road network of Xanthi city and specifically:**
 - ✓ to identify the most suitable range of data transmission between vehicles and infrastructure.
 - ✓ to evaluate the adequacy of RSU coverage based on their proposed placement.
 - ✓ to exploit the improvements in the driving behavior of vehicles.
- **Determine the necessity of implementing V2V and V2I communication support technology in the city's road network and recording improvements in terms of:**
 - ✓ the Traffic Management.
 - ✓ the arrival time of the vehicles at the destination.
 - ✓ the levels of CO2 emitted by vehicles.

Simulation Setup

The selection of the RSU placement points on the city map was based on data provided by Municipality and the Traffic Police Department of Xanthi, regarding areas where:

- Traffic lights are actually present (Figure on the left)
- Frequent congestion and road accidents have been observed
- Most traffic management issues have been reported

RSU Placement Points

Simulation Setup

- In order to provide a more adaptive and efficient signal control system we used actuated traffic lights that adapt their signal timing based on the current traffic conditions at the intersection.
- Actuated traffic lights use sensors or detectors to measure the traffic volume and adjust the signal timing accordingly.

Actuated Traffic Lights

Simulation Setup

Parameters

Parameters	Values
Simulation Region	City of Xanthi
Total Area	13,60 km ²
Number of Vehicles	1220
Number of RSU	30
Communication Range	100 – 600 meters
Simulation Duration	4600 seconds
Traffic Lights	Actuated
Number of Events	47
Event Start Time	Values between the 153rd and 350th second after the vehicle entry into the simulation
Event Duration	300 seconds
Communication Standard	IEEE 802.11p
Antenna Type	SampledAntenna1D
Transmission Power	20 mW
Transmission Rate	6 Mbps
Min Power Level	-110 dBm
Noise Floor	-98 dBm

- **SUMO (Simulation of Urban Mobility)** is an open-source microscopic traffic simulation software that is widely used for modeling and analyzing traffic in urban environments. Features and functionalities used:
 - ✓ Traffic flow modeling
 - ✓ Traffic signal control
 - ✓ Road Network modeling
- **OMNeT++ (Objective Modular Network Testbed in C++)** is a discrete event simulation framework that is widely used for simulating complex communication and network systems. It is an open-source, modular, and extensible platform that allows users to model and simulate various types of systems, including wireless networks, wired networks, sensor networks, and Internet of Things (IoT) systems. Features and functionalities used:
 - ✓ Component-based modeling
 - ✓ Discrete event simulation
 - ✓ Statistical analysis
- **VEINS (Vehicles in Network Simulation)** is an open-source simulation framework for vehicular network simulations. It is built on top of two other open-source simulation frameworks, OMNeT++ and SUMO, and it allows users to simulate communication and networking protocols in vehicular ad hoc networks.

- **L. Codeca, R. Frank, and T. Engel, authors of paper entitled "Luxembourg SUMO Traffic (LuST) Scenario: 24 hours of mobility for vehicular networking research,"** presented the LuST scenario as a mobility model for vehicular network simulation. Based on **Luxembourg's** road network, it incorporated real-world traffic patterns and communication protocols, such as IEEE 802.11p, for vehicular ad hoc networks. The simulation scenario emulated a 24-hour period of traffic in Luxembourg.
- **L. Codeca and J. Harri authored "Towards multimodal mobility simulation of C-ITS: The Monaco SUMO traffic scenario."** to create a comprehensive simulation framework for Cooperative Intelligent Transportation Systems (C-ITS) in **Monaco**. The paper utilized real-world data and traffic models to implement and evaluate the simulation scenario, which can provide insights into the feasibility of C-ITS in multimodal transportation systems.
- **S. Talib Hasoon and M. A. Mahdi** in "**A Developed Realistic Urban Road Traffic in Erbil City Using Bi-directionally Coupled Simulations,**" **S. Talib Hasoon and M. A. Mahdi** developed a realistic simulation method for urban traffic in **Erbil City** using bi-directionally coupled simulations. They combined the microscopic traffic simulator SUMO and the wireless network simulator NS-3 to model traffic flow and vehicular communication. By analyzing different traffic scenarios, the authors demonstrated the effectiveness of their approach in evaluating the performance of vehicular communication protocols under real-world traffic conditions.

Total number of warning messages sent

Total number of warning messages received

Total number of warning messages lost

Based on the results collected, we observed that the increase in transmission range has resulted in:

- **An increase in the amount of warning messages exchanged between vehicles and RSUs, due to**
 - ✓ the progressive increase in the number of vehicles and RSUs within the transmission range during the transmission period.
 - ✓ higher chance of multiple accidents within the same range
- **An increase in the amount of warning messages lost due to**
 - ✓ more obstacles along the signal path cause signal attenuation, reflection, and refraction
 - ✓ signal degradation due to reduced signal strength and noise/interference from external sources

- For the purpose of assessing the driving behavior of vehicles, our study involved the integration of six test vehicles.
- During the simulations, vehicles followed predetermined routes on the city road map, with specified departure and arrival points.
- The objective was to capture the variations in travel time of each test vehicle, following reception of warning messages.
- The total travel time for each test vehicle was recorded during simulations with different range coverage.

Based on the results, with the current configurations, a 400 meters transmission range resulted:

- In the most optimum range for accident avoidance
- In the most sensible coverage for adjusting course
- In decreased travel time to the destination

■ 100m ■ 200m ■ 300m ■ 400m ■ 500m ■ 600m

- **The following factors were measured for all vehicles:**
 - ✓ Total travel time
 - ✓ Total distance covered
 - ✓ Total maintained speed
 - ✓ Total CO2 emissions

- **To establish a basis for comparison, two new scenarios were simulated using current traffic conditions in the city of Xanthi:**

Worst case scenario

- Communication between vehicles and RSU was disabled
- Vehicle's route adjustment feature was disabled
- Traffic lights phase change set to static
- Vehicle numbers were maintained
- Scheduled accidents were maintained

Best case scenario

- Communication between vehicles and RSU was disabled (N/A)
- Vehicle's route adjustment feature was disabled (N/A)
- Traffic lights phase change set to static
- Vehicle numbers were maintained
- Scheduled accidents were deactivated

- Result analysis showed that simulations with communication range of 400 meters gave the best performance for the particular Case Study in the City of Xanthi.
- The observed values for all parameters of interest were significantly improved compared to the worst-case scenario values.

	No SA	With SA and V2X						With SA
	Best Case Scenario	100m	200m	300m	400m	500m	600m	Worst Case Scenario
Total Time (seconds)	514	773	640	568	551	670	720	833
Total Distance (meters)	7251	7323	7431	7591	7630	7520	7380	7251
Total speed (miles/hour)	14,1	9,5	11,6	13,4	13,8	11,2	10,3	8,7
Total CO2 (micrograms)	2055	3094	2560	2272	2204	2680	2880	3,332

V2X: Vehicle to Everything support

SA: Scheduled Accidents

- During the simulation with a communication range of 400 meters, vehicles took less time to reach their destination.

- It was observed that the total distance traveled by the vehicles was longer when with a transmission range of 400 meters was used. The average value of this parameter was found to be 7,630 meters.
- This increase in the distance traveled, which corresponded to about 5% compared to the values of the worst case scenario, was attributed to the ability of vehicles to modify their route after receiving the warning messages in order to avoid congestion.

- When a transmission range of 400 m was applied, the total sustained vehicle speed showed a significant increase. Specifically, the average total sustained speed was found to be 13.8 m/h, which indicates a 36.8% increase in speed compared to the worst-case scenario values.
- This increase was also due to that fewer vehicles were brought to a standstill.

- Moreover, it was observed that the average CO² emission level from the vehicles was significantly reduced in the simulation with a communication range of 400 meters, with the lowest value recorded at 2204 micrograms.
- The value was 33.9% lower compared to the worst-case scenario. The significant reduction in CO² emissions is attributed to the rerouting of vehicles, which helped to avoid congestion caused by accidents and prevented stop-and-go driving.

The results showed that for the particular case study in the City of Xanthi (including the specific vehicle transportation map, the location of the buildings, traffic light automations, and accident event configurations), we concluded that the optimal coverage range for achieving more effective V2V and V2I communication was 400 meters.

The range of 400 meters was found to be optimal for several factors:

- it was the best range for avoiding accidents and traffic congestion.
- it was the most reasonable coverage for adjusting course, based on the positioning points of the Roadside Units (RSUs).
- It resulted in reduced travel time to the destination compared to other ranges.
- It led to traffic management improvements in general.
- It achieved a reduction in CO² emission levels from vehicles compared to other ranges.

In order to further advance our ongoing research, we plan to conduct experiments and simulations. Specifically, our future work will entail the following:

- Test under different initial configurations to ensure optimum range based on different conditions.
- Examine optimal placement points for Roadside Units to ensure effective communication and coverage.
- Study the relationship between the frequency, timing and duration of accidents and congestion and develop strategies to mitigate both.
- Utilize real time live information.
- Develop intelligent routing algorithms through the use of reinforcement learning and traffic prediction models, trained on real data.
- Focus on emergency vehicles with particular requirements.
- Investigate the impact of electric and autonomous vehicles, on the emission level.
- Expand our research to include other cities by conducting similar investigations in Pafos, Cyprus to assess the efficacy of these technologies in different contexts for comparison.

Thank you